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CONTENTS

Articles

Attitude of Secondary School Teachers Towards Value Oriented Education <i>Dr. D. Aruna Jyothi</i>	1
Peace Education <i>Ms. Tanvi Gupta</i>	5
Role of Literature in Environment: A Critical Study of Wordsworth, Robert Frost and Emily Dickinson <i>Jarnail Singh</i>	9
Philosophical Vision of Pre-service Teachers - A Case Study <i>Mrs. T.R. Gayathri</i>	14
A Comparative Study of Physical and Health Education Paper in B.Ed. Curriculum in State Universities of Tamil Nadu <i>S.D. Subadra</i>	30
Teacher as a Motivator and a Performer in Teaching English Poetry an Analysis in the Perception of Secondary School Students of Kerala <i>Noora Abdul Kader</i>	35
Foreign Direct Investment in Retail Sector in India : A Critical Review <i>Dr. T. Rajasekar, Dr. I. Nagarajan</i>	39
Teaching Human Rights in the Era of Growing Terrorist Violence <i>Dr. Adam Paul P., B. Veerraju</i>	45
Education and Cultural Skills in the Context of Post Modernization at Elementary Level <i>Dr. R.S. Mani (R. Subramani Mudaliar)</i>	51
Policy Decision – Towards De-addiction <i>R.S. Kumareswaran</i>	60
Environmental Awareness Among School Students <i>Dr. Yodida Bhutia</i>	67
Emotional Intelligence and Self-Actualization of High School Teachers <i>Dr B. William Dharma Raja, M. Karthika</i>	72
Effectiveness of Teaching through Website Developed for Teaching of Computer Science at B.Ed Level <i>P. Ramalakshmi</i>	77
Development of a Three-tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics to Assess the Sixth-grade Students' Concept Achievement and Misconceptions About Geometry <i>Dr. Ritu Bala Aggarwal</i>	96
Television Viewers' Behaviour in Chittoor District Andhra Pradesh <i>Dr. M. Chandra Babu</i>	111

Development of a Three-tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics to Assess the Sixth-grade Students' Concept Achievement and Misconceptions About Geometry

Dr. Ritu Bala Aggarwal*

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study was to develop a three-tier concept achievement test (TTCATM) for assessing sixth-grade students' concept achievement and misconceptions about geometry. The first tier of an item on the test presents an ordinary objective type question, the second tier presents a set of reasons for the response given to the first tier and the third tier questions if examinees are confident for their responses to the first two tiers. In the light of the related literature, a preliminary draft of TTCATM was constructed using three main phases. In first phase Objective Type Achievement Test comprising of 100 questions was prepared. Interviews were held in order to get greater generaliability and create the distracters of the three-tier test. In this way, in third phase Preliminary Draft of TTCATM was prepared. It comprised of 107 questions. Then, final draft of TTCATM was prepared with 50 items having three tier tiers and was administered to 125 sixth-grade students. The validity of the TTCATM was established by means of quantitative methods in addition to the qualitative methods. To establish criterion validity a positive correlation coefficient was estimated between student scores and confidence levels. Experts opinion was sought to establish content validity. As well as, Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient came out to be 0.69, Consequently, the TTCATM assesses the concept achievement and misconceptions of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests. After the identification of achievements and prior to the identification of concept achievement: False positives and lack of knowledge have emerged in between. Also after the identification of errors and prior to the identification of misconceptions: false negatives and lack of knowledge have emerged in between.

Keywords: Development of a three-tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics, Mathematics, Concept Achievements, Misconceptions, Geometry, Three-Tier Test, Achievements, Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics, Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test.

INTRODUCTION

Elementary school stage is a significant period in students' mathematical development, a period in which they develop the capacity to understand and use mathematical knowledge. They become skilled to acquire and think critically about mathematical concepts and procedures. They crystallize their understanding of mathematical concepts and procedures and make the unconscious decision as to whether or not they will be successful in Mathematics. The concept formation developed in this golden period prepares platform for higher levels of education. The objective of this study is to create an informative resource intended for teachers of elementary school Mathematics, which identifies common mathematical misconceptions exhibited by students and to equip educators with valuable information so that they can begin to rebuild students' concept achievement of specific mathematical content areas and prevent certain misconceptions from occurring or continuing among their students.

ERRORS AND MISCONCEPTIONS

Mathematics education is based on problem-solving, application of knowledge and manipulations and when the students meet word-problems; their non-systematical and incomplete knowledge cause faults and conceptual mistakes. Generally when developing the problems, analyzing the problems, explaining the results and confirming processes aren't comprehended well, students go away from their own worlds. They exhibit large differences in their ability to grasp and understand mathematical concepts. This mismatch between the levels of pupils thinking and the intellectual demand of the subject-matter causes misconceptions in Mathematics. Diagnostic tests assess all the errors as misconceptions. But, all the errors are not misconceptions, since misconceptions happen when a person shows confidence in the objectively false concept (Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, 2008). Errors may be due to mistakes, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions among students (Eryilmaz and Surmeli, 2002; Pesman, 2005 and Kutuluay, 2005). Error is a deviation from accuracy or correctness and taken as wrong answers given to the objective type test items (first-tier) of three-tier tests. Misconceptions are false conceptions and can be assessed in three-tier tests by referring to incorrect answer in first-tier, incorrect reasoning in second-tier and confidence shown by the student in third-tier.

ACHIEVEMENT AND CONCEPT ACHIEVEMENT

Achievement is to get successfully the correct answer of a question. Concept achievement is the accomplishment of the concept and is regarded as identification of concept attributes, which can be generalized to newly encountered examples and discriminate examples from non-examples. Concept achievement is demonstrated by the use of the abstraction for classification, communication and problem solving, according to the standard of the culture. In concept learning an individual can discriminate, describe characteristics, use words and apply the knowledge (Vaidya, 1997). Concept achievement is achievement with correct reasoning and confidence. All achievements may not be concept achievement, since concept achievement happens when a person shows confidence for his/her answers and reasons (Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, 2008) and can be assessed in Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics by referring to correct answer in first-tier, correct reasoning in second-tier and confidence shown by the student in third-tier.

MEASUREMENT OF CONCEPT ACHIEVEMENT AND MISCONCEPTIONS

The researches seem to show that the first step in diffusing errors and misconceptions is to detect them by assessing their prior knowledge through informal quizzes, flow charts, concept maps and discussions that encourage students' freedom of expression (Myhill, 2000). It is important to know what prior knowledge students bring to learning environment in order to help them to construct new knowledge. In the past, students' prior knowledge was not considered seriously. When the misconception studies started to appear in the literature, science educators have focused on developing valid and reliable methods to identify them. Therefore, they proposed variety of methods to identify students' misconceptions such as various types of interviews, word associations, open-ended questions, multiple-choice tests, multiple-choice tests with explanation and two-tiered multiple choice tests (Al-Rubayea, 1996).

General achievement test attempts to assess students' performance in school subjects in terms of single score and the test does not identify specific errors and weaknesses etc. The diagnostic achievement tests, on the other hand intend to discover specific deficiencies in learning. The multi-tier concept achievement test has the ability to assess students' performance in the subject, errors committed by students in the test (wrong answers in the first tier) and to differentiate misconceptions from lack of knowledge as the sources of errors.

Achievement test is a standardized test intended to measure acquired learning, in a specific subject area such as reading or arithmetic, in contrast to an intelligence test, which measures potential ability or learning capacity. It is a set of questions asked to test what a person has learned from exposure to instruction (Anderson, 1972).

Instead of using norm-referenced testing in achievement, when we are to focus our measurement of learning tasks, criterion-referenced measurement is quite feasible and is preferred because of its descriptive nature (Gronlund, 1985). Although, criterion-referenced tests are very helpful in identifying the misconceptions of the students but their effectiveness is doubted as students do not justify their answers. To overcome this problem two-tier tests were used (Odom *et al.*, 1995; Cataloglu, 2002 and Tan *et al.* 2002). Two-tier tests include, in addition to selecting correct answer among the distracters, multiple reasons or justifications from which the students choose their reason for their response. Treagust (as cited in Odom and Barrow, 1995) described the item format of the two-tier multiple choice tests as the first tier consisting of a content question with two, three, or four choices. The second-tier consists of four possible reasons for the first part with three of them alternative reasons and one desired reason. The second-tier can also include a blank that students can write a reason for the first tier when they cannot see their reasons among the alternatives of the second-tier (Griffard and Wandersee, 2001).

The researchers also found that two-tier tests also overestimate the proportions of the misconceptions. In two-tier tests, the students are not asked for their confidence about their answers. Gap in knowledge cannot be discriminated by two-tier tests. So a third-tier is required that asks the students to show their confidence about the answers given in the first two tiers. Three-tier tests are very similar to the two-tier tests. In three-tier tests, an item has one additional tier which asks students confidence about the answer of the former two-tiers (Cataloglu, 2002). Pesman 2005; Turker 2005 and Ozlem 2007 developed three-tier test to assess the misconceptions of the high school students. Eryilmaz and Surmeli (2002) developed a three-tier test to assess the misconceptions of the high school students about heat and temperature. They found the students had misconceptions with an average 46% for the first tiers of the items, with an average 27% for the first two-tier of the items and with an average 18% for all three tiers of the items. From these results the researchers concluded that one tier and two-tier tests overestimated the proportions of the concept achievement and misconceptions. More over the methodology adopted in developing three-tier tests for assessing concept achievement and misconception in the previous studies provides a strong base for developing three-tier test in other subjects as well at different stages of formal education.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To construct and standardize TTCATM for elementary school students.
2. To assess the concept achievement of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests.
3. To assess the misconceptions of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests.

Hypotheses

1. TTCATM will assess the concept achievement of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests.
2. TTCATM will assess the misconception of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests.
3. After the identification of achievements and prior to the identification of concept achievement: false positives and lack of knowledge will emerge in between.
4. After the identification of errors and prior to the identification of misconceptions: false negatives and lack of knowledge will emerge in between.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted through descriptive method of research. The study was completed in two phases. In phase-A, TTCATM was constructed and standardized and in phase-B, field work was done.

Phase-A: Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics

The construction and standardization of TTCATM was based on the methodology devised and used by researchers to study errors and misconceptions in different subjects/specific area of content matter (Anderson, 1972; Gronlund, 1985; Odom *et al.*, 1995; Cataloglu, 2002; Tan *et al.* 2002; Eryilmaz and Surmeli 2002; Pesman 2005; Turker 2005 and Ozlem 2007)

To study the errors and misconceptions among elementary school students the TTCATM was constructed and standardized from the branch geometry in Punjab School Education Board prescribed Mathematics text book for 6th class.

Content of the unit Geometry from Punjab School Education Board prescribed text-book for 6th class was categorized under five headings:

1. *Basic Geometrical Concept:*

(i) Ray: Ray and its Properties.

(ii) Line: Line and its Properties.

(iii) Line-segment: Line-segment and its Properties.

2. *Angle:* Definition of Angle, Properties of Angle, Types of Angle: Zero Angle, Acute Angle, Right Angle, Obtuse Angle, Straight Angle, Reflexive Angle and Complete Angle.

3. *Pairs of Angles:* Definitions of Pairs of Angles, Properties of Pairs of Angles, Types of Pairs of Angles (Adjacent Angles, Linear Pair of Angles, Vertically Opposite Angles, Complementary Angles, Supplementary Angles), Relationship between Different Pairs of Angles.

4. *Pairs of Lines and Transversal:* Definition of Parallel Lines, Definition of Transversal, Pairs of Angles made by Transversal: (Exterior Angles, Interior Angles, Corresponding Angles, Alternate Interior Angles/Alternate Angles), Properties of Angles made by Transversal on Parallel Lines.

5. *Triangle:* Definition of Triangle, Properties of Triangle, Types of Triangle: Scalene Triangle, Isosceles Triangle, Equilateral Triangle, Acute Angled Triangle, Right Angled Triangle, Obtuse Angled Triangle.

A preliminary draft of TTCATM was constructed using three main phases explained below:

Phase 1: Objective Type Achievement Test

After obtaining a list of instructional objectives; outlining the course content, following table of specifications was prepared. Then 100 objective type test items were prepared. Two forms of recognition type objective test items were framed:

(i) Alternative response type test items – in these items two answers are given and the student has to tick mark the correct one and

(ii) Multiple choice type test items – in these items three or more than three possible answers are given and the student has to tick mark the correct one.

Table of Specifications: Objective Type Achievement Test

Sr. No.	Content	Objectives								Total
		Knowledge		Understanding		Application		Skill		
		MCT	ART	MCT	ART	MCT	ART	MCT	ART	
1	Ray	5	1		4	7			6	5
2	Line	9	2		8	11			10	5
3	Line-Segment	13	3		12	15			14	5
4	Angle	19,22, 24,27	16,18	21,23, 26	20, 25		17	28-34		19
5	Pairs of Angles		35-39		40-47	48-49				15
6	Transversal and Pairs of Angles		50,51, 55-58					54		7
7	Parallel Lines and Pairs of Angles made by Transversal		52, 59-61			62-64		53		8
8	Triangle	65, 83-85, 93	92,94	67,68, 72,75	74, 77-82	73,76, 96	86-88, 95, 97	66, 99	89-91, 69-71, 98,100	36
Total		34		27		17		22		100
Percentage		34%		27%		17%		22%		

Phase 2: Interviews

After the administration of the Objective Type Achievement Test, the researcher held interviews in order to get greater generaliability and create the distracters of the three-tier test. In the interviews, students were also asked additional questions to investigate the reasons for their answers and what lies behind their answer

Phase 3: Preliminary Draft of Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics

Seven questions were included in the test. Some questions were modified because students had some difficulty in understanding them. Therefore, It comprised of 107 items having three tier tiers.

Scoring:

Scoring of TTCATM was done by recording the students' answers on the test as correct/incorrect answer. The student got 1 mark for selection of correct answer in the first tier, 1 mark for corresponding correct reason in the second tier and 1 mark for showing confidence for these answers in the third tier otherwise the student got 0 mark.

If the student gives right response in first tier, right reason in second tier and shows confidence in third tier, total score for the question was 1. If in any one of the three tiers the student gets 0 marks, the total score was 0. In this way score of each student was calculated for all three tiers, first two tiers and third tier.

Selection of Items and Preparation of Final Draft of Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics:

The test was administered to 200 students. On the basis of the indices of item difficulty (0.16-0.25) and in view of judges, out of 107 items, 57 items were discarded and 50 items were selected. The distribution of the test items in terms of difficulty value is given in *Appendix 1*.

Final Draft of Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics

Final draft of TTCATM was prepared with 50 items having three tier tiers. First tier of each item comprised of objective type test items, second tier comprised of multiple-choice questions and the third tier comprised of alternative response type test items.

In the first tier, the student has to select the correct answer. The first tier of each item in the test was in an objective type (recognition type: Multiple-choice type and alternative response type) test format.

In the second tier, the student has to select/write reason for his/her selection of answer in the first tier. Second-tier is a multiple-choice test. While choosing the distracters for second tier, it was decided to keep the one showing misconception, one showing error *e.g.*, misread of statement etc., one showing unknowingness, one showing right concept achievement and one was left blank for any other alternate response.

In the third tier, the student has to show his/her confidence for the answers given in the first two tiers. The third tier of each item was in alternative response type (Yes/No) test format. Table of specification is as follows:

Table of Specification: Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics

Sr. No.	Content	Objectives								Total
		Knowledge		Understanding		Application		Skill		
		MCT	ART	MCT	ART	MCT	ART	MCT	ART	
1	Ray	1				3			2	3
2	Line	4				5				2
3	Line-Segment	6				7				2
4	Angle		9	11,12	10, 13		8	14,15, 16		9
5	Pairs of Angles		17,18		19-23	26, 27		24,25		11
6	Transversal and Pairs of Angles		28		29,30					3
7	Parallel Lines and Pairs of Angles made by Transversal		31		32,33	34				4
8	Triangle	35,42, 47	48	36, 37	40,41	43, 44	49		38,39,4 5, 46,50	16
Total		12		17		10		11		50
Percentage		24%		34%		20%		22%		100%

Administration:

The TTCATM was administered to 125 students of sixth class in various schools affiliated to Punjab School Education Board, Mohali to standardize the test and then the test books were scored. The obtained data was tabulated for further analysis.

Validity:

The validity of the test was established by using two qualitative techniques:

First, positive correlation between students' scores on the first two tiers and confidence level on the third-tier was found and criterion validity was established. Because it is expected that the students with higher scored would be more confident about the correctness of their answers if they understand what they read on a test (Cataloglu, 2002).

Second, content validity was established by giving the test to Mathematics teachers and Mathematics experts. Grammatical rules and language of the test were checked by language teachers.

Reliability:

The reliability of the test was calculated by calculating coefficient alpha, Kuder-Richardson reliability coefficient and came out to be 0.69.

Scoring of Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics

Keeping in view the purpose of the study, scoring was done in two phases. In the first phase, seven score were calculated:

(A) Seven Scores:

- (i) Concept Achievement Level-
 1. Only First Tier Score
 2. Only First Two Tier Score
 3. All the Three Tire Score
- (ii) Misconception Level-
 4. Only First Tier Score
 5. Only First Two Tier Score
 6. All the Three Tire Score
- (iii) Confidence Level-
 7. Only Third Tier Score

Scoring of Three Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics

Score	Tier 1	Tier 2	Tier 3	Total
Score 1	1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)			1
Score 2	1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)	1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)		1
Score 3	1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)	1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)	1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)	1
Score 4			1 (Correct Answer) 0 (Otherwise)	1
Score 5	1 (Misconception) 0 (Otherwise)			1
Score 6	1 (Misconception) 0 (Otherwise)	1 (Misconception) 0 (Otherwise)		1
Score 7	1 (Misconception) 0 (Otherwise)	1 (Misconception) 0 (Otherwise)	1 (Misconception) 0 (Otherwise)	1

In addition, in the second phase, nine dimensions were calculated:

(B) Nine Dimensions:

- (i) Concept Achievement Level-
 1. Achievement Scores (Score 1)

- 2. Concept achievement Scores (Score 3)
- 3. False Positives (Score 1 – Score 2)
- 4. Lack of Knowledge (Score 2 – Score 3)
- (ii) Misconception Level-
 - 5. Error Scores (Score 4)
 - 6. Misconception Scores (Score 6)
 - 7. False Negatives (Score 4 – Score 5)
 - 8. Lack of Knowledge (Score 5 – Score 6)
- (iii) Confidence Level-
 - 9. Confidence (Score 7).

Nine Dimensions

Sr. No.	Dimensions	Calculation
1.	Achievement Score	Score 1
2.	Concept Achievement Score	Score 3
3.	False Positives	Score 1 – Score 2
4.	Lack of Knowledge (Concept Achievement Wise)	Score 2 – Score 3
5.	Error Score	Score 4
6.	Misconception Score	Score 6
7.	False Negatives	Score 4 – Score 5
8.	Lack of Knowledge (Misconception Wise)	Score 5 – Score 6
9.	Confidence	Score 7

For example:

Question 43.

(a) A triangle with angles of measure 30°, 70°, 80° is called an acute angled triangle.

True/False

(b) Because:

(i) One angle is acute. ()

(ii) Two angles are acute. ()

(iii) Three angles are acute. ()

(iv) Any other _____

Yes/No

c. Are you confident?

Seven scores for this test item were calculated as:

(i) Concept Achievement Level-

1. **Only First Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'True' in 1st tier. And 0 otherwise.

2. **Only First Two Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'True' in 1st tier and answer 'Three angles are acute' in 2nd tier. And 0 otherwise.

3. **All the Three Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'True' in 1st tier, answer 'Three angles are acute' in 2nd tier and answer 'Yes' in the 3rd tier. And 0 otherwise.

(ii) Misconception Level-

4. **Only First Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'False' in 1st tier. And 0 otherwise.

5. **Only First Two Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'False' in 1st tier and answer 'One angle is acute' in 2nd tier. And 0 otherwise.

6. **All the Three Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'False' in 1st tier, answer 'One angle is acute' in 2nd tier and answer 'Yes' in the 3rd tier. And 0 otherwise.

(iii) Confidence Level

7. **Only Third Tier Score:** Student got 1 mark for answer 'Yes' in the 3rd tier. And 0 otherwise.

Achievement, false positives, lack of knowledge (concept achievement wise) and concept achievement is identified if a student scores one in first tier (score 1); one in first tier and zero in second tier (Score 1 – Score 2); one in first two tiers and zero in the third tier (Score 2 – Score 3); and one in each tier (Score 3) respectively. Error, false negative, lack of knowledge (misconception wise) and misconception is identified if a student scores one in first tier (Score 4); one in first tier and zero in second tier (Score 4 – Score 5); one in first two tiers and zero in the third tier (Score 5 – Score 6); and one in each tier (Score 6) respectively.

Phase-B Field Work

Sampling

1000 sixth grade students studying in government elementary, high and senior secondary schools of Punjab comprised the sample for present study, which includes equal number of male and female students and rural and urban students.

Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the schools and collected data from 6th class students on TTCATM.

ANALYSIS AND STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, percentage analysis, descriptive statistics, namely frequency distributions, central tendencies and variability were used. The results of analysis of data are shown in the following tables.

Table-1: Distribution of Achievement Scores of Elementary School Students on TTCATM

Class-Interval	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
36-38	1	0.10	100
33-35	17	1.70	99.90
30-32	92	9.20	98.20
27-29	234	23.40	89.00
24-26	351	35.10	65.60
21-23	204	20.40	30.50
18-20	71	7.10	10.10
15-17	29	2.90	3.00
12-14	1	0.10	0.10
Total	1000	100	

Mean = 25.11; Median = 25.17; Mode = 25.29; Variance = 13.84; S.D. = 3.72; Skewness = 0.03; Kurtosis = 0.268; Range = 24 (37-13)

Table-2: Distribution of Concept Achievement Scores of Elementary School Students on TTCATM

Class-Interval	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
18-20	4	0.40	100
15-17	54	5.40	99.60
12-14	185	18.50	94.20
9-11	350	35.00	75.70
6-8	307	30.70	40.70
3-5	96	9.60	10.00
0-2	4	0.40	0.40
Total	1000	100	

Mean = 9.38; Median = 9.30; Mode = 9.14; Variance = 10.11; S.D. = 3.18; Skewness = 0.36; Kurtosis = 0.269; Range = 18 (19-1)

Table-3: Distribution of Error Scores of Elementary School Students on TTCATM

Class-Interval	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
33-35	18	1.80	100
30-32	54	5.40	98.20
27-29	167	16.70	92.80
24-26	322	32.20	76.10
21-23	270	27.00	43.90
18-20	142	14.20	16.90
15-17	21	2.10	2.70
12-14	6	0.60	0.60
Total	1000	100	

Mean = 24.06; Median = 22.07; Mode = 18.09; Variance = 14.14; S.D. = 3.76; Skewness = 1.95; Kurtosis = 0.151; Range = 21 (34-13)

Table-4: Distribution of Misconception Scores of Elementary School Students on TTCATM

Class-Interval	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
15-17	1	0.10	100
12-14	26	2.60	99.90
9-11	186	18.60	97.30
6-8	449	44.90	78.70
3-5	318	31.80	33.80
0-2	20	2.00	2.00
Total	1000	100	

Mean = 6.65; Median = 6.58; Mode = 6.44; Variance = 13.62; S.D. = 3.69; Skewness = 0.21; Kurtosis = 0.173; Range = 15 (16-1)

Table-5: Distribution of Confidence Scores of Elementary School Students on TTCATM

Class-Interval	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
48-50	7	0.70	100
45-47	41	4.10	99.30
42-44	157	15.70	95.20
39-41	291	29.10	79.50
36-38	253	25.30	50.40
33-35	159	15.90	25.10
30-32	61	6.10	9.20
27-29	20	2.00	3.10
24-26	7	0.70	1.10
21-23	3	0.30	0.40
18-20	0	0.00	0.10
15-17	1	0.10	0.10
Total	1000	100	

Mean = 38.10; Median = 38.45; Mode = 39.15; Variance = 18.75; S.D. = 4.33; Skewness = -0.37; Kurtosis = 0.256, Range = 33 (49-16)

Table-6: Seven Scores on TTCATM (Percentage Analysis)

Level	Score	Tier	Average Score
Concept Achievement Level	Score 1	Only First Tier	50.22
	Score 2	Only First Two Tier	23.96
	Score 3	All The Three Tier	18.76
Misconception Level	Score 4	Only First Tier	48.12
	Score 5	Only First Two Tier	18.48
	Score 6	All The Three Tier	13.30
Confidence Level	Score 7	Only Third Tier	76.20

Table-7: Comparison of Nine Dimensions on TTCATM (Percentage Analysis)

Dimensions	Average Scores
Achievement	50.22
Concept Achievement	18.76
False Positives	26.26
Lack of Knowledge (Concept Achievement Wise)	5.20
Errors	48.12
Misconceptions	13.30
False Negatives	29.64
Lack of Knowledge (Misconception wise)	5.18
Confidence	76.20

MAIN FINDINGS

1. The distribution pattern of scores of elementary school students alongwith mean, median and mode values clearly indicates that

- (i) elementary school students have moderate level of achievement in Mathematics and low level of concept achievement in Mathematics
- (ii) elementary school students' level of errors is moderate and level of concept misconceptions is low in Mathematics
- (iii) elementary school students have high level of confidence in Mathematics.

2. The percentage of the concept achievement that the students had decreased with respect to the increase in number of tiers from 1 to 3 of the items. It is found the students had concept achievement with an average 50.22% (only first tier score) for the first tier of the items, with an average 23.96% (only first two tier score) for the first two tier of the items and with an average 18.76% (all the three tier score) for all three tiers of the items. Therefore, students had false positives with an average 26.26% (subtracting 23.96% from 50.22%). They had concept achievement wise lack of knowledge with an average 5.20% (subtracting 18.76% from 23.96%).

3. The percentage of the misconceptions that the students had decreased with respect to the increase in number of tiers from 1 to 3 of the items. The students had misconceptions with an average of 48.12% (only first tier score) for the first tier of the items, with an average of 18.48% (only first two tier score) for the first two tier of the items and with an average of 13.30% (all the three tier score) for all three tier of the items. Therefore, 29.64% (subtracting 18.48% from 48.12%) indicated false negatives and 5.18% (subtracting 13.30% from 18.48%) of the students had misconception wise lack of knowledge.

4. The results clearly indicate that the students had confidence with an average of 76.20%. Confidence of students on TTCATM had a range of 56.50% to 93.90%.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The researchers concluded that TTCATM assesses the concept achievement of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests.
2. The researchers concluded that TTCATM assesses the misconceptions of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests.
3. After the identification of achievements and prior to the identification of concept achievement: false positives and lack of knowledge have emerged in between.
4. After the identification of errors and prior to the identification of misconceptions: false negatives and lack of knowledge have emerged in between.

SUGGESTIONS

In the light of the findings of the present study, following are some suggestions that can be used by teachers and researchers to improve the Mathematics education:

- A teacher should focus on students' cognitive level to eliminate misconceptions and for better concept achievement level. The major focus of instructions should be on creating links between concrete experiences and abstract concepts.
- Teachers can use the TTCATM for formative evaluation to assess the misconceptions of the sixth class students about the geometrical concepts.
- Identification of students' misconceptions in Mathematics for the unit of geometry by Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics can give some feed back to the textbook editors.
- The results of the study show that between achievement and concept achievement false positives and lack of knowledge may emerge. This information would suggest the teaching practitioners to use a variety of teaching methods and combination of them to bridge this gap between achievement and concept achievement.
- The results of the study also show that students commit errors due to mistakes, lack of knowledge or due to misconceptions. These misconceptions are resistant to change and abrupt the learning process. The teachers are required to take students' misconceptions into account. The more the teachers know about their student's misconceptions the more guidance they will be able to provide them to learn. This would also contribute to the professional development of Mathematics teachers.
- This work has identified new material which can be utilized by Mathematics educators both in the classroom and in teachers pre- and in- service courses. This new material provides information about concept achievement and a number of misconceptions.
- Similar type of research can be undertaken for assessing errors and misconceptions in other school subjects as well at different stages of schooling.
- Similar type of research can be undertaken for the development of three-tier concept achievement tests for other concept areas of Mathematics learning.
- There is a need to identify the potential pathways that learners may follow while developing concept achievement. This approach has the advantage of helping teachers (pre-service and in-service) to prepare material to reduce the incidence of misconceptions formation and can also lead to more information on how learners actually, develop their knowledge. So research can be done which can give the knowledge of the development of specific pathways of conceptual development, the manner in which conceptual growth and development occurs.

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